

Proving Equivalence among Distinct Infinities

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Abstract:

The following is a proof that two infinite sets with zero elements in common can be equivalent to each other and converge to the same infinity despite seemingly going to two distinct infinities. Methods used are set theory, functors and category theory, graph theory, Euler-Lagrange equation and calculus of variations.

Introduction

Define two empty sets –

$$A \rightarrow \{\emptyset\} \quad (1)$$

$$B \rightarrow \{\emptyset\} \quad (1.1)$$

Define an operator on the sets, to bring each set to itself, from empty set to empty set.

$$\Delta: A \rightarrow A \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta: B \rightarrow B \quad (2.1)$$

Define an insertion operator on the set, so the sets are no longer empty:

$$\Delta t: A \rightarrow A' \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta t: B \rightarrow B' \quad (3.1)$$

Let the insertion operator act on the set for all times; require that for all time the union of the sets to be Empty, that is:

$$A' \cap B' = \emptyset; \quad (4)$$

$$0 < t < \infty$$

Therefore, we have two varying sets in number of elements, which have no common elements, and they aspire infinity in number of elements. Define a functor:

$$V: Set \rightarrow Graph \quad (5)$$

Operate the functor on the sets:

$$V: A \rightarrow A' \quad (5.1)$$

$$V: B \rightarrow B' \quad (5.2)$$

To obtain the trees of the sets A and B, define an ordering operator on the graph

$$O: A' \rightarrow A'(\text{desend}) \quad (6)$$

$$O: B' \rightarrow B'(\text{desend}) \quad (6.1)$$

To achieve an ordered graph whose vertices are descending in value; let each vertices have two children. We could have done the same before we switched to graph, by defining ordering operator on the sets. It does not matter. We did it on graph as computer scientists working often with them and we already possess sorting algorithms, so by doing it on graph maybe some practical uses can be found. Define additional functor:

$$Z: \text{Graph} \rightarrow \text{Top} \quad (7)$$

To obtain the varying trees on the topological space. Set the space to be complex analytical to ensure differentiation is possible at all times. Write down the Euler Lagrange for the varying trees:

$$L(A, A', t) \quad (8)$$

$$L(B, B', t) \quad (8.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial A} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial A'} \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial B} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial B'} \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) \quad (9.1)$$

We can also write this equation as the following

$$\Delta A - \Delta A' \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta B - \Delta B' \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) \quad (10.1)$$

But remember that ΔA is an empty set which stay as itself, meaning it does not vary, which means that in the topological setting $\Delta A = 0$ and $\Delta B = 0$.

The Euler Lagrange equation than becomes:

$$\Delta A' \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) = 0 \quad (10.11)$$

$$\Delta B' \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) = 0 \quad (10.12)$$

$$\Delta A' \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) = \Delta B' \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) = 0 \quad (11)$$

Meaning that all the elements insertion into the set itself vanished at the border. In the Graph representation we can say that the Top vertex and all his children converged into Zero, that despite that the infinities to have no elements in common, they converged to the Same value, so the total is the same for two distinct infinities at the time of examination.

$$\Delta A' \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) - \Delta B' \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) = 0 \quad (11.1)$$

Both have no common elements, Union is null, they have no similar vertices values in Common and their infinities are the same. That is by putting the trees on Topological space, Constructing the EL equation, and taking into Account **that we started with empty sets, Which stay as they are**, that is: $\Delta A = 0$ and $\Delta B = 0$.

Therefore, the variations over time must vanish, and so, despite they are different at all times In set representation and graph representation, they are equivalent, as they converge to the same value in graph theory, Top Vertex is equal to all children, even though the value of each children is different in both trees, they Summed to the same number and in topological representation the variations vanished at border. Concluding, if we start from two empty sets, which stay empty, insert infinite number of distinct elements to each one, which null as their union, we can reach the same infinity and so given the starting conditions to hold true, we can state:

End of Proof.